

IMPLEMENTATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION PROGRAM IN JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study delved into the status of implementation and the level of support of the administrators and faculty to Physical Education (PE) program, the teaching practices in PE, and the problems met in the implementation of the program during the School Year 2018-2019. The descriptive research design was used, with 165 school administrators and 797 PE teachers serving as respondents. A researcher-made questionnaire, interviews and focus group discussion served as tools to gather pertinent data. The study found out that school administrators and teachers believed that the objectives, teacher's qualification, physical facilities, assessment tools, program content/curriculum of PE program were effectively implemented. Moreover, school administrators and teachers manifest similar assessment on the level of support to PE program in terms of curriculum, developmental activities and athletic sports. In addition, the teachers are utilizing appropriate teaching strategies and assessment tools to effectively deliver PE instruction. Limited training venue for student athletes, lack of facilities required in conducting PE classes, and inadequate equipment and supplies for PE classes are the encountered problems in implementing PE program. Ultimately, the proposed management program comprises of several projects and activities that may help in improving the implementation of PE program in schools.

Keywords: Physical Education, PE curriculum, Quantitative Research, Philippines